

How metrology institutes can start working with DCCs without any prior knowledge

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1 Introduction

Replacement of paper-based calibration certificates with their digital counterparts Digital Calibration Certificates (DCCs) is vital for the digital transformation of many European industrial and legal metrology sectors. However, not all members of the European metrology community have access to the knowledge and capabilities needed for the implementation of DCCs. The DCC2GO project (DCC2GO, project webpage, <https://www.ptb.de/dcc2go/project/>, 2022) address this issue by supporting the implementation of DCCs within the European metrology community through the coordinated production and sharing of training material. This project benefits smaller and emerging National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes (DIs). This capacity building is needed to support a harmonised level of basic DCC knowledge and capabilities throughout the European metrology community as well as to address the needs of the wide range of stakeholders with an interest in DCCs.

This guideline is part of the DCC2GO starter kit (D. Baslev-Harder, 2023) It is providing hands-on guidance for the implementation of DCCs. Section 2 provides an overview on properties of the XML type and PDF/A-3 type DCCs and tools for the creation of these DCCs. Section 3 describes three different phases an organisation can go through to start working with DCCs. The phases comprise basic blueprints for actions that can be undertaken by an organisation. The suggested actions have been defined by experience of the DCC2GO project partners who are active at different stages of DCC implementation.

2 Two hands-on examples

XML type DCC (Siegfried Hackel, 2021) and PDF/A-3 type DCC (Gregor Boschung, 2021) are two frequently used representations today. An overview to these types is given below. The overview includes information on tools to work with these DCC types. A more detailed hands-on example for the creation of a DCC for temperature and pressure measurands with the XML type and PDF/A-3 type DCC is provided by the DCC2GO example suite (DCC2GO, DCC2GO examples for temperature and pressure DCCs, 2023).

2.1 XML type DCC

2.1.1 Introduction and advantages

The XML type DCC provides a fully machine-readable and harmonized representation of all information that needs to be provided in an ISO/IEC 17025-compliant calibration report today (ISO/IEC, ISO/IEC 17025:2018 certificates, 2018). It can be seen as an essential step forward from human based reports and processes towards allowing additional automated and machine-driven processing. Its high-level structure and concepts are outlined in figure 1. Some of its advantages are:

- Extensible Markup Language (XML) is a machine-readable data format that is easy to read for humans too and that can be viewed and edited on most computers with simple text editing tools.
- The XML type DCC format is defined by a schema file (PTB, DCC - Digital Calibration Certificate Schema, 2023) which allows automated validation of the DCC content and its compliance to ISO/IEC 17025 requirements (ISO/IEC, ISO/IEC 17025:2017 General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories, 2017).
- The XML type DCC can contain all kinds of attached data in different file formats such as figures, binary data records, or the calibration certificate in a human readable form

such as PDF.

- The XML type DCC is ready for integration within highly automated processes in industries. These include, for example, Industry 4.0 applications or cyber physical systems where a media-break free and full machine-actionable end-to-end exchange of data is needed.
- The XML type DCC development was started in 2017 and has gained substantial maturity. Today, a larger international community of metrology organisations and calibration laboratories are progressing its development and harmonization under coordination of PTB (Al Mamun et al, 2023).
- The XML DCC is not only for calibration data from metrology institutes but addresses the whole calibration chain from an accredited calibration laboratory to end users.

The XML DCC is well documented. You will find the XML scheme, examples, presentations and documentation at the DCC homepage (PTB, DCC website, 2023).

Figure 1: High level structure of the XML DCC. International standards such as ISO/IEC 17025, the SI and other form the basis of a hierarchical data structure which provides administrative data and measurement results as well as comments and human readable pages.

2.1.2 Tools for creating an XML type DCC

XML is widely used in software for machine-readable data. Thus, most Integrated Software Development Environments (IDEs) provide the tools to read and write XML DCC data (Group, 2023). The XML type DCC schema (PTB, DCC - Digital Calibration Certificate Schema, 2023) can be included in these tools to allow validation of the XML DCC against the schema.

Very useful for starting to work with the XML type DCC is the GEMIMEG DCC tool (PTB,

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GEMIMEG Tool, 2023). This tool is a website-based online editor for creating simple DCCs. A user will not need to be able to write XML but can fill in administrative data and measurement data from calibration in easy-to-use web forms. The tool is then able to create a valid XML type DCC from the input. In addition, it is possible to convert the XML to a human-readable PDF document which could be appended to the XML file.

A simple example for temperature calibration data was created in the DCC2GO project using the GEMIMEG tool. The example data is available at Zenodo (DCC2GO, DCC2GO examples for temperature and pressure DCCs, 2023). Figure 2 shows the administrative data editor of the GEMIMEG tool and Figure 3 is a screenshot of the XML that was created for the example. The DCC2GO starter kit provides more tools that are available for the XML type DCC.

Figure 2: User editor for administrative data of XML DCC in the GEMIMEG tool.

```

1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
2 <dcc:digitalCalibrationCertificate xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns
   :dcc="https://ptb.de/dcc" xmlns:si="https://ptb.de/si" xsi:schemaLocation="https://ptb.de/dcc
3 - https://ptb.de/dcc/v3.2.0/dcc.xsd" schemaVersion="3.2.0">
4   <dcc:administrativeData>
5     <dcc:dccSoftware>
6       <dcc:name>
7         <dcc:content>GEMIMEG tool</dcc:content>
8       </dcc:name>
9       <dcc:release>v1.3.0</dcc:release>
10    </dcc:dccSoftware>
11  </dcc:administrativeData>
12  <dcc:coreData>
13    <dcc:countryCodeISO3166_1>GB</dcc:countryCodeISO3166_1>
14    <dcc:usedLangCodeISO639_1>en</dcc:usedLangCodeISO639_1>
15    <dcc:mandatoryLangCodeISO639_1>en</dcc:mandatoryLangCodeISO639_1>
16    <dcc:uniqueIdentifier>DCC2GO-Temperature-DCC-Example</dcc:uniqueIdentifier>
17    <dcc:identifications>
18      <dcc:identification>
19        <dcc:issuer>calibrationLaboratory</dcc:issuer>
20        <dcc:value>2023/04/0001</dcc:value>
21        <dcc:name>
22          <dcc:content lang="en">Order no.</dcc:content>
23        </dcc:name>
24      </dcc:identification>
25    </dcc:identifications>
26    <dcc:beginPerformanceDate>2023-04-13</dcc:beginPerformanceDate>
27    <dcc:endPerformanceDate>2023-04-13</dcc:endPerformanceDate>
28    <dcc:performanceLocation>laboratory</dcc:performanceLocation>

```

Figure 3: XML DCC created with the GEMIMEG tool for the DCC2GO temperature example.

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2.2 PDF/A-3 type DCC

2.2.1 Introduction and advantages

One of the steps towards machine readable DCCs which are used by many calibration laboratories, is the use of PDF/A-3 for transferring the data from the calibration laboratory to the customer.

There are numerous advantages in using PDF/A-3 rather than paper certificates and other digital formats.

- The PDF/A-3 is an ISO standard, developed with the purpose of being archivable. This gives a certainty that the documents will still be valid within any foreseeable future regardless of developments in digital infrastructure and formats (ISO, 2020).
- The PDF/A-3 can be digitally signed. This can be used to ensure, that the document received by the customer is identical to the one created by the calibration laboratory.
- The PDF/A-3 (third version of PDF/A) can contain attached files. This has the potential of facilitating further developments for the calibration laboratories within the field of DCCs, as extra data can be attached to the PDF document. As such, an XML type DCC can be created as described in section 4.1. This XML type DCC can be used for machine readability and full automation of implementation of calibration results at the consumer site. At the same time, the same calibration data can be used for creating the PDF certificate, which is human-readable.

As can be seen from the above, the PDF/A-3 cannot in itself work as a machine readable DCC, but it can facilitate as a digitally signed container for the DCC, while also having the function of presenting the data in a human readable format. The structure of distributing calibration data in two parallel methods, both the PDF and the attached DCC must be verified to ensure that data from the two sources is identical. This, however, can be considered to be regulated within ISO 17025, and should not pose a problem to the calibration laboratory.

2.2.2 Tools for creating a PDF/A-3 type DCC

As PDF/A-3 is an ISO standard, many tools exist for creating the format from various sources. It is possible to create PDF/A-3 from excel-sheets and word-files, scanned from paper, or build using LaTeX (LaTeX-Project, 2023).

Assuming that an XML type DCC has already been produced, a PDF/A-3 containing the same information as the XML will be straight forward to create, populating a LaTeX-template with the relevant data from the XML followed by running the LaTeX interpreter. The original XML document can be attached to the PDF/A-3 DCC in the process, as described by METAS in the documentation of their eCertificate tool (METAS, 2023) This of course requires, that the exact XML schema is known in order to extract the correct values.

If instead the calibration data is already saved in a database, both the XML and the LaTeX source file can be populated directly from here, ensuring the data source is identical for the two documents.

Once the PDF/A-3 containing the XML (or other DCC format) is produced, the document can be signed and shipped, and any tampering with either the PDF file or the attached XML file can be identified.

Populating the XML and LaTeX file can be performed using any scripting language, capable of reading XML data or by other means extracting data from such files.

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Figure 4: PDF/A-3 type DCC created with the METAS eCertificate tool for the DCC2GO temperature example.

3 Blueprint for starting to work with DCCs

An organisation will have to consider different kinds of actions at different phases of the DCC implementation. DCC2GO collected actions undertaken or planned to be undertaken by the DCC2GO project members. Based on the collection, a blueprint was developed for the implementation of DCCs. The blueprint introduces three different phases for the implementation. The phases refer to early-, medium- and longer-term actions.

3.1 Phase 1 – Preparation and exploration

This first phase work is done to identify the benefits and challenges of DCCs and leads toward defining the scope and requirements for the digital DCC infrastructure needed at the metrology institute and customers. It is crucial to identify technical possibilities and limitations and get an initial estimate for the cost and benefits of implementation.

Six crucial steps in this phase are to

1. Identify existing DCC technologies.
2. Identify which calibration labs will have the largest benefit of implementing DCC.

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3. Identify which customers will have the largest benefit of implementing DCCs.
4. Identify what implications it will have when implementing DCCs.
5. Establishing an initial management strategy for implementation work.
6. Undertake initial pretest internally and with customers.

The first step of getting familiar with the existing technologies and their maturity, is important in understanding benefits, possibilities, and challenges which the implementation of DCC's provide. The DCC2GO guides are a good starting point for this process but should be followed by exploration of available updated digital resources and affiliated developments in the metrology community.

More detailed descriptions of actions in each step are listed below. The timeframe refers to a period of the first year when starting to work with DCCs (nearer-term actions).

Step 1: Identify existing DCC technologies

The first step would start by forming a small internal pilot group in your organisation made up of representatives from management, calibration, and IT-experts. Throughout the first phase, this group would steer preparation and exploration work. On a technical side, the calibration and IT-experts start to investigate existing solutions for DCCs, differences in their maturity regarding machine-actionability (ISO/IEC, ISO/IEC SMART standards, 2023) and requirements for implementation and use. The aim of this work is to determine which DCC formats would be suitable for the start. The DCC2GO training compendium and starter kit will provide help to obtain an initial overview on existing formats, technical and management aspects.

Step 2: Identify which calibration labs will have the largest benefit of implementing DCC

The existing calibration services in your laboratory will be reviewed to identify those laboratories and calibrations with the largest benefit from introducing DCCs and where an introduction of DCCs would be easy. Different criteria could be applied to evaluate the suitable calibrations. For example,

- a high demand by customers for specific calibration results as DCC,
- availability of harmonized DCC for a calibration service making an implementation easy,
- measurement data and certificates are already created and stored digitally in a calibration laboratory which would make it easy to create a DCC on top of it,
- a high number of calibrations as well as larger amounts of data that would benefit from automation and provision in machine-readable formats.

Step 3: Identify which customers will have the largest benefit of implementing DCCs.

An early exchange with customers to inform about DCCs is important. It will help the pilot team to evaluate where an introduction of DCCs would be most valuable and which customer needs would have to be considered when starting to implement a first DCC. In addition, stakeholder input is needed to assess the timescales when customers plan to start using DCCs. This activity may be conducted in the form of webinars or short workshops with a small number of selected stakeholders in your organisation, e.g., calibration laboratories and representatives from accreditation.

Step 4: Identify what implications it will have when implementing DCCs

The pilot group continues its work to establish the first DCC example for an existing calibration service found to be of high benefit. This involves exploring approaches and tools for the DCC

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creation, storage of DCC data, signing DCCs, and providing DCCs to customers. In this step, it will also be discussed what is needed to start recording measurement data in digital format. The work will allow the pilot group to initially identify potential implications that the introduction of DCCs will have on required resources, for example additional equipment that would be needed in laboratories and offices as well as changes of processes.

Step 5: Establish an initial management strategy for implementation work.

Based on the experience gained from steps 1 to 4, an initial strategy and roadmap could be established for the wider implementation of DCCs in your organization. Such a strategy would consider the DCC types that will be implemented. Furthermore, the strategy contains next steps that need to be taken to consolidate DCC creation for the example investigated by the pilot group and to establish the necessary resources for the wider implementation and handling of DCCs.

Step 6: Undertake initial pretest internally and with customers.

The first phase is concluded by typically having performed a pretest for handling a DCC in a realistic calibration service setup. This includes having gone through a complete process of calibration where at the end a DCC is created and provided to a customer. In this stage, the DCC may be delivered to the customer as an addition to a legally binding human readable calibration certificate. Outcomes of the pre-testing will contribute to further refinement of strategies and roadmaps. It will also help to inform further stakeholders and customers about the implementation of DCCs in your organisation.

3.2 Phase 2 – Implementation and validation

With input from the explorations made in the first phase, the second phase is considering a step-by-step implementation of DCCs in a wider range of laboratories. In the medium-term it would comprise the topics listed below

Topic 1: Establish signatures for DCCs

Develop and implement processes and tools for cryptographically protecting the DCCs (electronic signatures, verification of correctness of data, protection from manipulation of data, etc.). The DCC2GO starter kit provide a separate guideline dedicated to this topic (D. Baslev-Harder, 2023).

Topic 2: Implement archiving of DCCs

Develop and implement a concept how to archive DCCs for the time your organization needs to keep a record (e.g., with proper backup systems). This could also include considerations to track a history of instruments for internal purpose, this may for example comprise your organization introducing e-file systems or other longer-term useable data bases.

Topic 3: Pilot testing of laboratory delivering DCC to customers

The pilot laboratory from phase 1 is developing the DCC creation to become an established part of its calibration service. At the same time, other laboratories within the company start piloting and setting up DCCs for their calibrations.

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Topic 4: Update of company policies and quality management systems

Policies of the company are checked if they need to be updated to allow DCCs to be issued to customers. This could include requirements coming i.e., from EA guidelines or national accreditation guidelines. At the same time, the quality management (QM) guidelines and documentation of the organisation need to be updated to take account of the work with DCCs.

Topic 5: Roadmap for institute implementation of DCC and dissemination

The management will extend the roadmap for the DCC implementation by actions for a wider introduction of DCCs in the organisation (as part of its calibration services). This will also comprise first internal trainings and knowledge transfer activities as well as trainings and workshops with stakeholders (customers, national accreditation, etc.) who are the users of DCCs. The roadmap can also contain actions to keeping up to date with international developments, updates of DCC systems, and engagement within communities dealing with the harmonization of DCCs for relevant measurands.

3.3 Phase 3 - Dissemination, Training, Maintenance, and Automation

As in phase 1 (Preparation and exploration), dealing with short term aspects, and phase 2 (Implementation and validation), dealing with medium-term aspects, certain topics are of interest, in the longer term. These include, amongst others, dissemination, training, and maintenance. In the long-term implementation of DCCs, the order in which the different topics are handled are of minor importance. Most probably, they will all be handled simultaneously, as this is part of a continuous process.

Topic 1: Maintenance

A crucial topic for longer term implementation of DCCs is to maintain them. While this might sound like a broad topic, in this document, it refers to the ability to read old DCCs and constantly offering to deliver the newest implementation of the DCC, all in accordance with the FAIR principles (GO-FAIR, 2023).

One of the most vital elements of long-term implementation of DCCs is their proper archiving. The archiving must follow the rules laid out in ISO 17025, i.e., for as long as it is contractually obligated.

Within the DCC it should be stated, which version of the relevant schema is being used, allowing users to track down the specified schema. As such, it is also a good idea to keep a local copy of the different schema versions, as it can never be ensured, that they are available at the source repository after a given timeframe. Furthermore, software, capable of interpreting the DCCs, should also be archived. Although customer interpretation of the DCC is not the responsibility of the DCC, it is still good practice to ensure this possibility.

The above concern requires, that a proper archiving methodology is practised in the laboratory. Using a proper archiving system will furthermore make it easy to remove DCCs which are obsolete, when they have exceeded the archiving requirements stated in ISO 17025. Ensuring the correct link between the DCC and the software can either be ensured by adding the software details in the DCC or as an attribute in the database.

Keeping up with new versions of the DCC schema is also a requirement in the longer term implementation of DCCs. Most probably, the majority of the schema updates will be minor and

not affect the implementation at the specific laboratories, but not being able to deliver the DCC which supports the newest schema can be a deal-breaker for some customers. Hence ensuring that the local implementation of the DCC schema is in place is practically a necessity. Furthermore, software tools could be used to migrate data from old versions of DCCs to the newest schemes.

Finally, it can easily become a requirement for certain customers to request a DCC following a specific schema version. This backwards compatibility must be considered when updating the tool for creating DCCs.

Topic 2: Training & Dissemination

To gain the most value of the DCCs in the organisation, it is beneficial that as many users as possible can figure out how to use them, both internally and externally. As such, a key topic in the longer term is training and dissemination, not just of key staff, but of day-to-day users of DCCs. This will also help in the global implementation of DCCs in the organisation.

Typically, DCCs will be implemented in one working group with a laboratory at a time, e.g., due to the personnel who will oversee the practical implementation. During the implementation, the laboratory staff will need training in how the introduction of the DCCs will influence their work when creating certificates, how to record readings from references and customer equipment into the system, etc.

Just as the training of the internal staff is important, customers might also need assistance when they are implementing DCCs in their organisation. Here, close dialogue with the customer is of high importance to ensure that the format is as expected, i.e., that the DCC follows the correct schema used at the customers location.

Topic 3: Automation

A key advantage in introducing DCCs and other forms of digitalisation into the laboratories is the possibility to automate processes and optimize workflows. This includes automated test setups, automatic logging of reference data as well as automated readings of the device under test (DUT).

The automation of processes in the laboratories and automatic reading of the instruments will assist in improving the collection of valuable meta-data from the calibration, such as specific environmental data, timestamps etc. as well as reducing the risk of errors in the process, such as manually writing down incorrect values, setting the equipment up for the wrong set-points, etc. Although DCCs do not require automated processes, it should be seen as a golden opportunity to start working within this area too. Having automated processes in the lab will bring forth the full potential of DCCs, as systems can be created which more easily gather all the right information from the calibration to auto-generate the documents. All of this will bring a higher level of quality assurance into the calibration chain, giving added value to the customer.

Topic 4: Calibration Requests

Longer term benefits of DCCs can also include the implementation of Digital Calibration Requests (DCR) into the organisation's infrastructure (PTB, Digital Calibration Request, 2023). DCRs enable services where customers digitally request a calibration with specific conditions (points, uncertainties, etc.). The DCR can provide the requirements set by the customer to an

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automatic calibration procedure for the DUT.

There is still much discussion on exactly how DCCs and DCRs should be implemented at a national, regional, and international level, and whether DCCs should be disseminated through clusters located at e.g., the National Metrology Institutes or directly from the issuing laboratory. Until this discussion has reached a definitive conclusion, it will not be possible to give specific guidelines as on how the exact implementation of some of these long-term issues should be carried out.

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6 Common Abbreviations

DCC	Digital Certificate of Calibration
DI	Designated Institute
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LaTeX	document preparation system for high-quality typesetting
NMI	National Metrology Institute
PDF	Portable Document Format
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	eXtensive Markup Language

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